

Human Reference Atlas

Glossary

Human Reference Atlas Standard Operating Procedures Glossary

Library of terms included in Human Reference Atlas Standard Operating Procedures

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The Human Reference Atlas Standard Operating Procedures Glossary is a library of specialized terms used in Human Reference Atlas SOPs. This is a living document. The version shared here is the version in use at the time of publication.

Definitions

The below definitions are used in Human Reference Atlas Standard Operating Procedures. When available, definitions were taken from the [HuBMAP Dictionary](#), and aligned with standard terminologies used in relevant fields.

3D collision: The intersection of 2D or 3D bounding-box volumes or surface polygon meshes.

3D model: Digital object with a shape and size defined by polygon meshes (vertices and edges) that can be used to represent the real-world form of anatomical structures, cells, or proteins in 3D.

3D printing (or additive manufacturing): The construction of a three-dimensional object from a CAD model or a digital 3D model. The term "3D printing" can refer to a variety of processes in which material is deposited, joined or solidified under computer control to create a three-dimensional object, with material being added together (such as plastics, liquids or powder grains being fused together), typically layer by layer.

3D reference object: Polygon mesh of 3D spatial objects (for example, anatomical structures), their object node hierarchy, materials, and surface color and texture. They are created by medical illustrators with the involvement of subject matter experts following standard operating procedures.

(spell out) AMAP: See working definition in the AMAP SOP, currently under development

anatomical structure (AS): An anatomical structure is a distinct biological entity with a 3D volume and shape, for example, an organ, functional tissue unit, or cell.

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Anatomical Structure Cell Type Populations (ASpop): A collection of cell type annotations for a specific anatomical structure, which captures the number of cells per cell type. Metadata includes an ontology ID, donor sex, anatomical structure label, the cell type annotation tool used to assign cell types, and a list of datasets from which the data was sourced.

angiosome: An angiosome is a region of muscle, skin, or bone supplied by a primary artery.

antibody reproducibility: Consistent performance of an antibody across lots or batches.

antibody sensitivity: The ability of an antibody to detect target antigens of varying abundance. This can be influenced by assay specific factors such as the formulation and concentration of the antigen, antigen retrieval, temperature, and time.

antibody specificity: The ability of an antibody to recognize and bind to its intended epitope and not bind to other off-target epitopes. This can be determined with appropriate positive and negative controls.

antibody validation report (AVR): Document providing details on the characterization of individual antibodies for multiplexed antibody-based imaging assays. These details include target protein information (e.g., target name, UniProt accession number), and antibody information (e.g., RRID, host organism, vendor, catalog number, lot number). AVRs also provide details on controls used for antibody characterization and validation (positive and negative tissues, cell lines, isotype controls, etc), exemplar imaging data, and information on other antibodies tested.

application programming interface (API): Software that allows two applications to communicate with each other.

approved documents: Once an SOP is approved by the PI and any additional approvers, it is in full force and the procedures should be followed as described until such time as the SOP is superseded with a newer version or marked obsolete.

ASCT+B MASTER table: The first ASCT+B table for an organ system to which other ASCT+B-like information may be compared, using the ASCT+B Reporter compare feature.

ASCT+B Reporter: The ASCT+B Reporter is a visualization tool for displaying anatomical structures, cell types and biomarkers (ASCT+B) tables for different human organs developed by domain experts. The tables are used to develop a common coordinate framework (CCF) of the healthy human body, <https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-asct-reporter>.

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ASCT+B tables: Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) Tables are authored by multiple experts across many consortia. Tables capture the partonomy of anatomical structures, cell types, and major biomarkers (such as gene, protein, lipid, or metabolic markers). Cellular identity is supported by scientific evidence and linked to ontologies.

assay metadata: Assay specifications for a given dataset such as instrument settings, reagent providers, lot numbers and reagent/sample concentrations.

Atlas enriched dataset graph: A graph for highest quality datasets used for Human Reference Atlas construction (it has an extraction site, cell type population, and publication or provenance on a major atlas portal), enriched with additional metadata, computed by HRApop.

AutoMated Alignment and Projection (AMAP): This acronym refers to the process of aligning two mesh-based 3D models and projecting the underlying data between human atlas systems for data and code interoperability. In the HRA this is used to project registered tissue blocks from a specific source organ to a reference organ.

AVR document: The AVR document (saved as a PDF) is completed by the AVR author and provides detailed information on antibody characterization. One AVR document is submitted per protein target.

Azimuth: Azimuth is a web application that uses an annotated reference dataset to automate the processing, analysis, and interpretation of a new single-cell RNA-seq or ATAC-seq experiment. See <https://azimuth.hubmapconsortium.org>.

bimodal network: A network involving two node types and the relationships between them.

biomarkers: Molecular, histological, morphological, radiological, physiological or anatomical features that help to characterize the biological state of the body. HRA biomarkers can be measured to characterize or identify a cell type. They include genes (BG), proteins (BP), metabolites (BM), proteoforms (BF), and lipids (BL).

Blender: Blender is an open-source 3D computer graphics suite of software tools. It supports the full 3D creation pipeline.

Blood Vasculature Geometry Table: A table that lists geometric properties, such as length and diameter, of selected blood vessels.

Blood Vasculature-Organ Crosswalk Diagram: This crosswalk table is an essential part of the Human Reference Atlas's goal to build a Vasculature Common Coordinate Framework (VCCF), which uses vascular pathways to describe the location of cells

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throughout the body. The diagram enables domain experts to visualize and discuss the crosswalks, review them for accuracy, and suggest corrections.

boolean operation: In a 3D editor two 3D objects can interact in a boolean operation to create a new object, cutting away everything of object A where it intersects with object B (A minus B), or only the area where both objects intersect is kept (A AND B).

block array: A set of blocks dissecting the virtual organ sample into a specific, user-requested grid. The individual blocks are arranged in columns and rows, and are separated by cutting slots. Unlike the full millitome, block arrays are only for use in virtual environments.

CCF tools are scripts written to test the part/is_a relationships implicit in the ASCT+B tables for validity against ontology databases such as Uberon and Cell Ontology. See [this GitHub repository](#) for detailed workflow.

Cell DIVE: The Cell DIVE multiplexed imaging solution is an integrated system for imaging 60+ biomarkers from one tissue sample at the single-cell level. The tissue-preserving staining and dye inactivation workflow and advanced image processing enables a more comprehensive understanding of the tissue microenvironment than has been available with traditional chromogenic- or fluorescence-based imaging (Gerdes et al. 2013).

cell distance metrics: Measurement that represents the proximity between cell centroid and the outer boundary of vasculature cells.

cell suspension: Single cells or nuclei isolated from a tissue (e.g., using enzymes or mechanical means) for single cell assays, for example, before sc/snRNA-seq assay is run.

cell type: Mammalian cells are biological units with a defined function that typically have a nucleus and cytoplasm surrounded by a membrane. Each cell type may have broad common functions across organs and specialized functions or morphological or molecular features within each organ or region. Tissue is composed of different (resident and transitory) cell types that are characterized or identified via biomarkers.

cell type annotation (CTann): the process of identifying and labeling distinct cells. Azimuth and other tools are used to assign cell types to cells from sc/snRNA-seq studies. In the Human Reference Atlas, manually compiled crosswalks are used to assign ontology IDs to these cell types.

cell type annotation crosswalks: A collection of CSV files that link cell type labels generated using cell type annotation tools to Cell Ontology or Provisional Cell Ontology IDs. This harmonizes cell types across ASCT+B tables and other digital objects that are part of the Human Reference Atlas.

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cell type population: A list of the cell types included in a collection of cell at different scales, such as an anatomical structure, extraction site, or dataset. Currently in the Human Reference Atlas, cell type populations consist of a listing of unique cell types, the number of cells per cell type, and mean biomarker expression values per cell type.

Cellular Senescence Network (SenNet): The Cellular Senescence Network Program was established and funded by the Common Fund at the National Institutes of Health to comprehensively identify and characterize the differences in aging cells across the body, across various states of human health, and across the lifespan. SenNet will provide publicly accessible atlases of senescence using data collected from multiple human and model organism tissues.

centroid: The geometric center of an object or shape, in this case, the geometric center of a cell nucleus.

creator: The creator(s) of specific digital object versions.

CNS Center: The Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science Center is a research center in the Intelligent Systems Engineering Department of the Luddy School of Informatics, Computing, and Engineering at the University of Indiana Bloomington.

CO-Detection by indEXing (CODEX): see **PhenoCycler**

comma-separated values (CSV): This is a text file that has a specific format which allows data to be saved in a table structure.

common coordinate framework (CCF): As used in the Human Reference Atlas, this consists of ontologies and reference object libraries, computer software (e.g., user interfaces) and training materials that (1) enable biomedical experts to semantically annotate tissue samples and to precisely describe their locations in the human body (“registration”), (2) align multi-modal tissue data extracted from different individuals to a reference coordinate system (“mapping”), and to (3) provide tools for searching and browsing data at multiple levels from the whole body down to single cells (“exploration”). See also <https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf/>.

competition dataset: The final dataset that is provided to the participating teams and is made available on the competition webpage of Kaggle’s competition platform. The dataset comprises a publicly available training dataset, a public test set which is not directly available to the participating teams but is used to score their solutions which are visible to the participating teams, and a private test set which is not accessible, directly or indirectly, to the participating teams.

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competition metric: A machine learning and/or data science metric used to score Kaggle competition solutions against gold standard dataset labels.

conjugate: Fluorescent dye, oligonucleotide, metal or enzyme covalently attached to a primary or secondary antibody that is used for downstream detection of the antibody bound to its target in/on a cell.

cosine similarity: Measures the cosine of the angle between two vectors, with 1 indicating identical vector directions and 0 indicating no similarity.

crosswalk: An ontological mapping of terms in the Human Reference Atlas digital objects (such as, for example, 2/3D reference objects, OMAPs, Azimuth references) to ontology terms in the ASCT+B tables.

Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science (CNS) Center is a research center in the Intelligent Systems Engineering Department of the Luddy School of Informatics, Computing, and Engineering at the University of Indiana Bloomington.

cyclic immunofluorescence (CyclIF) is a public-domain method for performing highly multiplexed immunofluorescence imaging using a conventional epifluorescence microscope. It uses simple reagents and existing antibodies to construct images with up to 30 channels by sequential 4- to 6-channel imaging followed by fluorophore inactivation.

cytokit: An open-source software package for quantifying and analyzing spatial, morphological and other properties of individual cells in large fluorescent microscopy datasets.

data mirror: Replicating data wholesale from one site to another site. This can mitigate the risk of loss of data and provides a periodically updated backup of the original data.

DataCite: A leading global non-profit organization that provides persistent digital object identifiers (DOIs) for research data and other research outputs.

dataset: A collection of experimental data.

dataset graph: A JSON-LD file containing a graph of RUI-registration, donor, experimental (e.g., links to cell by biomarker [CxB] H5AD files or CTpop), literature, and provenance data.

digital content creation software: Software used to create and edit digital media, including images, video, audio, 3D models, animations, and more. Blender is one example used frequently in the Human Reference Atlas.

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digital object (DO): Human Reference Atlas digital objects are the data components for generating the HRA knowledge graph. ASCT+B tables, 3D reference objects, and OMAPs are examples of HRA digital objects. Digital objects are often connected to specific ontologies via crosswalk tables.

digital object identifier (DOI): Centrally registered identifier composed of a string of numbers, letters and symbols used to uniquely identify an article or document with a permanent web address or Uniform Resource Locator (URL).

distance calculation: A mathematical computation to determine the shortest path between two given points. In 2D and in 3D space, we use the Pythagorean theorem; for 3D it is $(x_1-x_2)^2 + (y_1-y_2)^2 + (z_1-z_2)^2 = \text{distance}^2$, where x, y, and z are the coordinates of two cells.

donor: An individual from whom tissue was obtained.

draft document: A document in progress and not yet approved. This might be a revision of an existing SOP or a new document. It is important to note that a document is in draft form rather than in force. This is indicated with a red DRAFT added just after the title in the header of the document.

enrichment code: An umbrella term for scripts executed towards the end of an HRA code pipeline. The purpose is harmonizing or adding existing metadata, e.g., for HRA digital objects during HRA knowledge graph construction and for dataset graphs during HRApop construction.

Exploration User Interface (EUI): An interface developed by MC-IU to explore tissue, see <https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/ccf-eui>.

extraction site: Digital, 3D representation of a tissue block. If the Registration User Interface is used to register tissue, then each site has a unique ID; data on size, location, and rotation in 3D in relation to an Human Reference Atlas reference organ; a listing of all anatomical structures that the cuboid intersects with (bounding-box collision by default); and metadata on who registered it.

fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS): Fluorescence-activated cell sorting uses fluorescently tagged antibodies to cell surface markers most commonly to sort populations of cells into different containers based on markers present.

Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles: a way of sharing data to maximize its utility, as described in <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>.

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Filmbox (FBX) file format: A proprietary file format (.fbx) developed by Kaydara and owned by Autodesk since 2006. It is used to provide interoperability between digital content creation applications.

fixed frozen: Method of tissue preservation where samples are placed in fixative (e.g., formalin), cryoprotected with sucrose, frozen in molds with optimal cutting temperature (OCT) media, and stored at -80C.

flattened data table: A database that stores data in a plain text file where each row of the spreadsheet file holds one record, with fields separated in columns.

flow cytometry: Similar to FACS without sorting cells into containers, visually represents cell populations based on fluorescent marker presence or absence.

formalin fixed paraffin embedded (FFPE): Most common form of tissue preservation where tissues have undergone chemical fixation by saturating them with formalin followed by embedding in paraffin wax to enhance preservation and facilitate sectioning of the tissue. Samples are stored at room temperature.

fresh frozen (FF): Method of tissue preservation where samples are frozen at ultralow temperature without fixative (fresh), immobilized in cryosafe media (e.g., OCT, carboxymethyl cellulose), and stored at -80C.

functional tissue unit (FTU): A functional tissue unit is the smallest tissue organization, i.e. a set of cells, that performs a unique physiologic function and is replicated multiple times in a whole organ. FTUs can be hierarchically nested.

geometric property: A physical characteristic of a blood vessel, such as length, luminal diameter, and outer diameter. It may be recorded as a single value if measured from an individual vessel or as a mean, standard deviation, or range if measured across multiple specimens.

GitHub: An online service for version control and code-sharing.

GLB file format: Also called GL Transmission Format Binary file (.glb), this is a 3D file format specification, see <https://docs.fileformat.com/3d/glb>.

Globus: Globus is software-as-a-service for research data management, used by hundreds of research institutions and HPC facilities worldwide for secure, reliable file transfer, sharing and publication.

Groups.io: Groups.io is an email groups service that enables users to find and start groups, sync members, and archive conversations with hashtags.

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healthy tissue: Pathologically unremarkable tissue that can be used to derive the function of healthy cells. What counts as healthy is influenced by normal aging, underlying comorbidities and medical interventions before tissue donation.

hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) stain: Histology stain that is widely used as a gold standard for pathological evaluation of tissue sections.

histogram: A graphical representation of the distribution of a dataset.

HIVE: Integration, visualization and engagement teams which are part of the Human BioMolecular Atlas Program.

HIVE processed data: Experimental data that has been normalized, transformed, filtered or otherwise processed by the HIVE to facilitate interpretation.

HuBMAP: The Human BioMolecular Atlas Program is a consortium composed of diverse research teams funded by the Common Fund at the National Institutes of Health. HuBMAP is developing the tools to create an open, global atlas of the human body at the cellular level. These tools and maps will be used to accelerate understanding of the relationships between cell and tissue organization and function and human health.

HuBMAP Ingest Portal: The HuBMAP Ingest Portal is where HuBMAP members generate HuBMAP IDs.

Human Reference Atlas (HRA): The Human Reference Atlas is a comprehensive, high-resolution, three-dimensional, multiscale atlas of all the cells in the healthy human body. The Human Reference Atlas provides standard terminologies and data structures for describing specimens, biological structures, and spatial positions linked to existing ontologies.

Human Reference Atlas release version: New and updated data is released twice a year on June 15 and December 15. The HRA uses semantic versioning to differentiate these bi-annual updates.

Human Reference Atlas Knowledge Graph (HRA KG): The HRA Knowledge Graph (KG) defines and provides the core data structures that are used to store, link, and query HRA data.

Human Reference Atlas Literature (HRAlit): Scholarly publications linked to Human Reference Atlas digital objects to provide scholarly evidence.

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Human Reference Atlas Cell Type Populations (HRApop): HRApop is a standardized 3D dataset linking high-quality experimental data to Human Reference Atlas digital objects. HRApop quantifies the number of cells per cell type within anatomical structures, extraction sites, and datasets while harmonizing cell type annotations using crosswalks to common ontologies. HRApop is published as versioned releases and serves as a healthy reference for researchers aiming to clarify mechanisms underlying cellular interactions as well as cellular and tissue level disease progression.

iCalendar (ICS) file: An ICS file is a calendar file saved in a universal calendar format used by several email and calendar programs, including Microsoft Outlook, Google Calendar, and Apple Calendar. It enables users to publish and share calendar information on the web and over email.

image pyramid: A collection of images at different resolutions which facilitates “zooming” depth when viewing.

image segmentation: A process in digital image processing that divides an image into multiple segments or sets of pixels. Each segment corresponds to different parts or objects present in the image. In a medical context, it often refers to differentiating and labeling distinct structures or regions within a scan or microscopy image. It can also be used to isolate anatomical structures such as nuclei, cellular membranes, cells, or functional tissue units in 2D or 3D.

imaging mass cytometry (IMC): Multiplexed imaging method that employs metal-conjugated antibodies applied in a single master mix to tissues. Target-specific antibodies are detected using laser ablation coupled to mass cytometry (Giesen et al. 2014).

immunofluorescence (IF): Laboratory technique used to visualize proteins in cells or tissues using specific primary antibodies conjugated to fluorescent dyes.

immunohistochemistry (IHC): Laboratory technique used to visualize proteins in cells or tissues using specific primary antibodies conjugated to chromogens.

Immunostaining with Signal Amplification by Exchange Reaction (Immuno-SABER): A highly multiplexed and signal amplification method free of in situ enzymatic reactions that utilizes oligonucleotide-conjugated antibodies and complementary fluorescent imagers (Saka et al. 2019).

interactive visualization: Graphical representations that allow users to engage with and manipulate the displayed data, typically in real-time.

International Standard Book Number (ISBN): A 13-digit number that is used as a unique identifier for a specific book, a book edition, or any other book-like products. An ISBN number

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can be used to identify the book's code digits, language, publisher, book title, edition, and format.

Iterative Bleaching Extends Multiplexity (IBEX): An open source iterative immunolabeling and chemical bleaching method for high-content imaging of diverse tissues (Radtke, Chu, et al. 2022; Radtke et al. 2020).

iterative indirect immunofluorescence imaging (4i): A cyclic high-content imaging method for visualizing cellular and subcellular structures in situ (Gut et al. 2018).

lab processed data: Experimental data that has been normalized, transformed, filtered or otherwise processed by the data provider to facilitate interpretation.

Linked Open Data (LOD): A method for sharing data in standard, non-proprietary formats, and deeply interlinked with other data resources.

lipid: Lipids are molecules that contain hydrocarbons and make up the building blocks of the structure and function of living cells. Examples of lipids include fats, oils, waxes, certain vitamins (such as A, D, E and K), hormones and most of the cell membrane that is not made up of protein.

lookup table: A tabular mapping of one entity to another, e.g., a phone book (name to number). The millitome lookup table links identification numbers in one system (e.g., Millitome IDs) to corresponding identification numbers in another system (HuBMAP IDs).

Mapping Component-Indiana University (MC-IU): The Indiana University team is one of two teams in the HuBMAP consortium tasked with building an atlas of tissue maps. These two teams are identified as mapping components, as opposed to components or teams that develop tools or provide infrastructure support.

MACSima Imaging Cyclic Staining (MICS): Immunofluorescent imaging method for hundreds of protein targets across a single specimen at subcellular resolution based on cycles of staining, imaging, and erasure. This method uses photobleaching of fluorescent labels of recombinant antibodies (REAffinity Antibodies) or release of antibodies (REAlase Antibodies) or their labels (REAdye_lease Antibodies). The commercial platform (MACSima Imaging System) is a fully automated instrument based on fluorescence microscopy, recombinant ready-to-use antibody-fluorochrome conjugates, sample carriers and a MACS iQ View Analysis Software for data analysis (Kinkhabwala et al. 2022; Schäfer et al. 2021).

Maya Embedded Language (MEL): Maya Embedded Language is a scripting language used in Maya.

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metabolite: A substance made or used when the body breaks down food, drugs or chemicals, or its own tissue (for example, fat or muscle tissue).

millitome: Millitomes provide guidance on how to partition an organ, often a complete organ. Millitomes can include either a 3-dimensional mold that physically holds an organ for partitioning, or a drawing of an organ that is used as a guide by a surgeon when they partition an organ free hand, or both. Using a millitome ensures that tissue sample locations show correctly in the Exploration User Interface.

modal: A modal is an overlay that appears in an application interface above all other content, that usurps control or focus from the parent content, and typically prompts the user to perform an action (e.g. entering login credentials) or providing the user with information (e.g. help text or video).

modality:

multiplexed ion beam imaging (MIBI): Multiplexed imaging method that employs metal-conjugated antibodies applied in a single master mix to tissues and an ion beam for tag ionization (Angelo et al. 2014; Lomeli et al. 2021).

nucleus: The cell nucleus (plural nuclei) is a membrane-bound organelle found in eukaryotic cells that contains most of the cell's genetic material.

OBJ file format: Also called Wavefront Object file (.obj), this is a widely used, open-standard 3D file format that stores the geometry of 3D models—including vertex positions, faces, texture mapping coordinates, and normals—in a human-readable text format. OBJ files are compatible with most 3D modeling, printing, and visualization tools, and can reference material and texture data stored in associated .mtl files, but do not contain animation information.

Object File Format (OFF): Used to represent 3D geometry through polygons of the model surface with any number of vertices. You can see an example of an OFF file at https://shape.cs.princeton.edu/benchmark/documentation/off_format.html.

obsolete documents: When a document is tagged as being obsolete, it means that it is no longer appropriate for the purpose it was created for. For example, a very old procedure that is no longer applicable to the current process due to advancements in technology would be considered obsolete. As such, a new SOP would reflect the current process and typically a new SOP would have a different number and reference the obsolete SOP as the predecessor.

Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID): Unique identifier number researchers own and control that connects the ID with professional information — affiliations, grants, publications, etc. and can be used during the publication process. See <https://orcid.org>.

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optical coherence tomography (OCT): Optical Coherence Tomography is an imaging technology that employs long wavelength, near-infrared light to obtain sub-surface images of translucent or opaque materials. OCT is primarily used for detecting eye diseases like macular degeneration. The imaging technology differs from conventional CT.

optimal cutting temperature compound (OCTcompound): Optimal cutting temperature compound (OCTcompound) is used to embed tissue samples prior to frozen sectioning on a microtome-cryostat.

ontology: A set of subject area concepts (here, anatomical structures, cell types and biomarkers), their properties and the relationships between them. Ontologies used in the Human Reference Atlas include Uberon and Cell Ontology (CL).

Organ Mapping Antibody Panel (OMAP): A comprehensive panel of curated antibodies that identifies the major anatomical structures and cell types in a specific organ. The selected antibodies are optimized for a tissue preservation method (i.e., fixed, frozen) and multiplexed imaging modality (e.g., CODEX, Cell DIVE) through published protocols (protocols.io) and AVR.

OMAP table: File required for all contributed OMAPs. The file is created in a shareable Google sheet that summarizes all antibodies and reagents used in the OMAP and provides details on the successful use and rationale for selected antibodies. The published DOI'd versions exist as both .csv and Excel.

OMAP Description Document: File required for all contributed OMAPs. The text file provides a short description (< 300 words) of the OMAP with details on the tissue preservation method, multiplexed imaging method, fiducial (e.g., DAPI), antigen retrieval conditions, and total number of antibodies used. This document also lists cell types and structures not covered by the OMAP and names of contributors (authors and reviewers), and funding sources.

organ mold: This refers to the organ-shaped cavity in the middle of the millitome. It is designed to hold the organ tightly in place while being cut.

partonomy: A classification hierarchy that represents part-whole relationships.

pathway: The paths through the body formed by blood vasculature, lymph vasculature, and PNS.

Persistent Uniform Resource Locators (PURL): A uniform resource locator (URL), i.e., location-based uniform resource identifier or URI, that is used to redirect to the location of the requested web resource. PURLs redirect HTTP clients using HTTP status codes.

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PhenoCycler: This multiparameter imaging method, formerly known as CO-Detection by indEXing (CODEX), relies on oligonucleotide-conjugated antibodies and the cyclic addition and removal of complementary fluorescently labeled oligonucleotide probes. The commercial fluidics and high-plex image acquisition platform (Akoya Biosciences, Marlborough, MA) for this method enables whole slide imaging of up to 100 biomarkers on tissue samples in situ (Black et al. 2021; Goltsev et al. 2018; Kennedy-Darling et al. 2021).

polyclonal antibody: A mixture of antibodies derived from distinct B-lymphocyte populations that detect multiple epitopes within the same immunogen. Production of polyclonal antibodies typically involves the collection of blood from the immunized animal, isolation of the immunoglobulin fraction, and affinity purification to remove non-specific antibody populations. These antibodies can be used for research purposes to detect the corresponding antigen in or on cells in a tissue. An antibody binds to an antigen or protein target directly. Primary antibodies are most often conjugated covalently to a fluorescent dye, oligonucleotide, metal or enzyme for downstream detection methods. Note that polyclonal antibodies can exhibit significant lot-to-lot variability, which can impact their performance in experiments. This variability arises from differences in immunization protocols, host animals, and conditions during production.

polygon mesh: A collection of vertices, edges and faces defining the shape of a polyhedral object, e.g., tissue block cuboids or reference objects denoting anatomical structures.

primary antibody: An immunoglobulin made in response to a specific antigen (often a protein) that causes an immune response in an animal. These antibodies can be used for research purposes to detect the corresponding antigen in or on cells in a tissue. An antibody binds to an antigen or protein target directly. Primary antibodies are most often conjugated covalently to a fluorescent dye, oligonucleotide, metal or enzyme for downstream detection methods.

Prioritized OMAP Target: A protein target that defines major anatomical structures and/or cell types within an OMAP. OMAP authors and reviewers can designate up to 25 biomarkers in their OMAP as Prioritized OMAP Targets in the rationale section of their OMAP Table. All core markers should be designated as Prioritized OMAP Targets.

principal investigator (PI): Person who is responsible for the overall conduct of the research at a given site.

private leaderboard: The leaderboard used for the final rankings of a Kaggle competition, where teams are ranked on their final two selected entries. This leaderboard is not visible to the participating teams during the competition. It uses a private test dataset for calculating the scores.

procedure: A step by step description of how to accomplish a set of related tasks. Procedures usually describe a specific way of undertaking a process in a detailed way.

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process: A process is a series of tasks that produce an outcome. Process can be thought of as the “what are we doing” rather than the “how we are doing it.”

Protégé: An ontology editor, see <https://protege.stanford.edu>.

proteoform: all of the different molecular forms of a protein product from a single gene that can be found, including changes due to genetic variations, alternatively spliced RNA transcripts and post-translational modifications.

provenance: A record of the chain of sample custody, sectioning and processing.

public leaderboard: The leaderboard used for team rankings during a Kaggle competition based on their best scoring entry. This leaderboard is visible to the participating teams during the competition. It uses the public test dataset for calculating the scores.

PubMed Central reference number (PMCID): This unique identifier links to full-text papers in PubMed Central, a free full-text archive of biomedical and life sciences journal literature at the U.S. National Institutes of Health's National Library of Medicine (NIH/NLM).

PubMed reference number (PMID) links to abstracts in PubMed, which comprises more than 34 million citations for biomedical literature from MEDLINE, life science journals, and online books.

QA/QC metrics: Quality assurance metrics are used to determine if the quality of assay results meets the required standards (eg: signal:noise thresholds). A **Quality control** is used to test the assay components like reagents & instruments to confirm they meet quality requirements (eg: testing positive/negative controls). Quality controls are part of quality assurance.

QuPath: QuPath is open source software for bioimage analysis. QuPath is often used for digital pathology applications because it offers a powerful set of tools for working with whole slide images, but it can be applied to many other kinds of image as well.

raw data: Experimental data that requires processing for interpretation.

registration set (see also dataset graph): Grouping of tissue blocks by the study or paper in which they were published. Each set has a human-readable registration set name, a machine readable Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI), and it links to a paper DOI and tissue block IDs.

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registration: The process of mapping tissue samples into reference anatomical bodies. It combines spatial alignment (positioning samples relative to the reference) with semantic annotation (linking sample regions to defined anatomical structures) to enable comparison and integration across datasets.

Registration User Interface (RUI): Registration user interface developed by MC-IU, available via HuBMAP Data Ingest Portal and at <https://apps.humanatlas.io/rui>.

Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs): Unique identifiers for referencing a biomedical reagent or resource. See <https://www.rrids.org>.

Resource Description Framework schema label (Rdfs:label): is a human-readable version of a resource's name and is a standard for data interchange, developed and agreed upon by World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) and used for the preferred name in an ontology.

reviewer: Subject matter expert who reviews digital objects for accuracy.

ROBOT: an ontology tool for automating ontology workflows, see <http://robot.obolibrary.org>.

role: One's position on a team.

RUI-registered: Tissue spatially and semantically registered to the Human Reference Atlas using the Registration User Interface (RUI).

sample: An organ, tissue, or section thereof obtained from a donor.

sample ID: An ID that uniquely identifies a tissue block, and links it to donor and other metadata. In the HuBMAP consortium, this is referred to as the sample ID.

Scalable Vector Graphics (SVG): A web-friendly vector file format. As opposed to pixel-based raster files like JPEGs, vector files store images via mathematical formulas based on points and lines on a grid.

scRNAseq: single cell RNA sequencing, an assay that measures polyadenylated RNA molecules in an individual cell.

secondary antibody: An antibody that is used to indirectly visualize a primary antibody. Secondary antibodies are made by immunizing a host animal with antibodies of a different species (e.g., goat anti-rabbit secondary antibodies derived from goat immunized with rabbit IgG) and are used to detect species- and isotype-specific primary antibodies (e.g., goat anti-rabbit IgG paired with primary antibody made in rabbit). Secondary antibodies are most often conjugated covalently to a fluorescent dye, oligonucleotide, metal or

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enzyme for downstream detection methods and are sometimes used to amplify the signal of the antigen-bound primary antibody.

secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS): A technique capable of imaging tissues, single cells, and microbes revealing chemical species with sub-micrometer spatial resolution (Anderton and Gamble 2016). SIMS is used as a multiplexed imaging method by detecting metal-conjugated antibodies where an ion beam generates ejected ions detected with a mass spectrometer.

semantic annotation: The semantic annotation ontology term associated with a 3D object that can be used as an object name and to search for or filter the object.

single cell proteomic data: Data from single cell studies using CODEX, Cell DIVE, Ibex, CyCIF, or other assays that detect proteins in situ in a tissue, consequently enabling protein expression quantification.

single cell transcriptomic data: Data from single cell or single nucleus (sc/sn), high-throughput suspension-based studies that measure polyadenylated ribonucleic acid (RNA) molecules in an individual cell.

single nucleus chromatin accessibility and polyadenylated RNA expression (SNARE): This assay generates sequence data on both transposase-accessible chromosomal DNA and polyadenylated RNA in the nucleus of the same cell.

skos:exactMatch: Indicates that two concepts are semantically equivalent across different vocabularies or ontologies. Used when the annotated cell type and the referenced Cell Ontology term refer to the same biological entity.

skos:narrowMatch: Indicates that the source concept is more specific than the target concept. Used when the annotated cell type represents a subtype or specific grouping not fully captured by the broader Cell Ontology term.

Slack channel: Channels are spaces for all the people, tools, and files you need to get work done in Slack. You can create channels for different teams, topics, and projects to bring order and clarity to work.

Slack workspace: Every Slack team has its own workspace. A Slack workspace is a space that brings together all the channels and chats of a company, where all communication, file sharing, and conference calls take place.

snATAC-seq: single nucleus ATAC (Assay for Transposase Accessible Chromatin) sequencing, an assay that sequences exposed surfaces of open chromatin in an individual nucleus.

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snRNA-seq: single nucleus RNA sequencing, an assay that measures polyadenylated RNA molecules in an individual nucleus.

snRNA-seq/snATAC-seq: an assay simultaneously measuring both RNA and open chromatin in an individual nucleus.

spatial: Residing in 2 or 3 dimensional spatial coordinates.

spatial process and relationship modeling (SPRM): SPRM is a statistical modeling program for microscopy that performs cell clustering & segmentation based on pixel intensities across multiple channels.

standard operating procedures (SOPs): SOPs are issued to specifically instruct team members in areas of responsibility, procedural steps, appropriate specifications and required records. SOPs outline procedures, which must be followed to support the reproducibility of scientific research. Procedures can take the form of a narrative, a flow chart, a process map, computer screen printouts or combination of all or any other suitable form, however must be written in appropriate, effective grammatical style (e.g., plain English).

step: One action in a series of actions.

stitching: Image stitching aligns overlapping edges of multiple image “tiles” captured across a tissue sample to produce a single, large image.

sterolithography (STL): STL is a file format commonly used for 3D printing and computer-aided design (CAD). STL is also sometimes also referred to as Standard Triangle Language or Standard Tessellation Language. Each file is made up of a series of linked triangles that describe the surface geometry of a 3D model or object. The more complex the design, the more triangles used, and the higher the resolution.

subject matter expert (SME): A person with extensive knowledge about a given topic. With regards to the Human Reference Atlas, an SME may have substantial experience with one, or all, aspects related to the cellular composition of human tissues, tissue preservation methods, multiplexed imaging techniques, integration with ASCT+B Reporter, and affinity reagents such as longitudinally stable antibodies.

superseded documents: Superseded documents are those that have been subjected to minor and perhaps some major revisions, but the scope and intent of the document remains the same. Process changes are typical in some types of documents such as standard operating

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procedures (SOP). When changes occur the SOP is updated to the next revision number and the previous version is tagged as superseded.

Tagged Image File Format (TIFF): A flexible and widely supported raster image file format used for storing high-quality graphics, photographs, and scanned documents, often retaining rich color depth and lossless compression.

task: A piece of work, usually undertaken as part of a larger project.

tissue-based cyclic immunofluorescence (t-CyCIF): A cyclic high-content imaging method employing commercial antibodies and diverse microscope configurations, based on the approach of chemically inactivating fluorophores after iterative rounds of immunofluorescence (Lin et al. 2015, 2018; Black et al. 2021). See <https://www.cycif.org>.

tissue block: A sample or specimen derived from an organ or tissue including subsections thereof obtained from a donor that has a unique ID and links to donor, organ extraction site, processing, preservation and other metadata. The locations of tissue blocks are registered using the Registration User Interface.

tissue block ID: The ID that uniquely identifies a tissue block and links it to the relevant metadata such as donor data. In HuBMAP, this is the Sample ID.

tissue mapping center (TMC): A type of HuBMAP project that generates and contributes data to the consortium.

tissue section: A thin (several microns) section of a tissue block usually obtained using a cryotome or microtome. Tissue sections inherit the location and rotation of their parent tissue block. The thickness and number of tissue sections is captured in an input field inside the RUI.

tissue suspension: A tissue prepared for bulk analysis.

typology: A classification that represents general types, e.g., cell types or biomarker types.

Uberon: Uberon is an integrated cross-species anatomy ontology covering animals and bridging multiple species-specific ontologies.

Uniform Resource Identifier (URI): Identifies a resource and differentiates it from others by using a name, location, or both and contains components like a scheme, authority, path, and query.

Uniform Resource Locator (URL): Identifies the web address or location of a unique resource; however, its authority consists of a domain name and port.

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united file: The united file is a GLB 3D object that contains all the modeled organs in the Human Reference Atlas.

Unity: A suite of software tools used to create interactive three-dimensional, two-dimensional, virtual reality, and augmented reality experiences.

Vascular Common Coordinate Framework (VCCF): A proposed approach to use vasculature as a coordinate system to map all the cells in the human body.

violin plots: Visual representations combining aspects of box plots and density plots to display data distributions.

virtual reality (VR): a simulated three-dimensional environment that users can interact with in a seemingly physical and immersive way using specialized electronic equipment.

Visible Human (VH): The Visible Human Male and Visible Human Project datasets are provided by the National Library of Medicine.

Web Ontology Language (.OWL) file format: The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) Web Ontology Language is a Semantic Web language documented at <https://www.w3.org/OWL>.

working group (WG): a committee or group formed to study and report on a particular question and make recommendations based on its findings. Open working groups encourage participation from people working in other consortia rather than just those working on HuBMAP.

YAML file: YAML is a human-readable data serialization language typically used for writing configuration files.

YouTube: A free online video-sharing platform.

Zenodo: Zenodo is an open-access repository, see <https://about.zenodo.org>.

Zotero: Zotero is a bibliographic management tool for collecting, organizing, citing, and sharing research, see <https://www.zotero.org>.